

CASE STUDY OF PROVISION OF TRADE SERVICES TO VILLAGE POPULATION IN SAMARKAND REGION

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Abstract. *In this article, the provision of commercial services to the rural population, as a socio-economic category closely related to meeting the population's demand, "the evaluation of the effectiveness of the provision of commercial services to the rural population and determination of its indicators is considered.*

Keywords: *villagers, trade services, efficiency, strategy, service, delivery.*

Introduction. In the context of the globalization of world trade, it is crucial to increase consumer loyalty through the prism of satisfaction with trade services. Thus, the main trend in 2020 is called "...the modern consumer's desire to improve the efficiency of the choices made in relation to everyday objects and experiences, as well as the compliance of shopping services with the expectations of purchase and delivery." goods ...". In this regard, it is the demand of the time to conduct scientific research on the development and efficiency of the service sector in rural areas on the basis of foreign experience.

During the years of independence, a number of state programs were developed and implemented in the Republic of Uzbekistan, which made it possible to significantly improve the level of trade services in rural areas. Based on the concept of "...rapid development of the service sector", the tasks of further development of the provision of trade services to the rural population of the republic were determined. Improving the efficiency of the consumer market in the village is a necessary condition for solving the envisaged tasks. The lack of development of the retail trade network, the lack of modern forms of retail trade in rural areas, and the insufficient quality of trade services determine the need for in-depth scientific study of this topic.

Research methodology. Systematic approach, abstract-logical thinking, grouping, comparison, factor analysis, selective observation methods were used in the research process.

Analysis and results consist in developing proposals and recommendations on increasing the efficiency of trade services to the rural population in the conditions of modernization of the economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

To achieve this goal, the following tasks were set:

critical analysis of the concept of "effectiveness of providing trade services to the rural population" as a socio-economic category closely related to meeting the population's demand;

development of scientific-methodological bases for evaluating the effectiveness of providing trade services to the rural population and determining its indicators;

analysis of the state of the main organizational forms of providing trade services to the rural population and development of scientific recommendations for their development;

development of strategic directions for increasing the efficiency of trade services in rural areas;

Based on the information of the Samarkand region, a comprehensive study of the state of the consumer market and the provision of trade services in rural areas was conducted. In the process of research, we studied and analyzed statistical data on the development of retail trade in

Samarkand region. The data of the last years show a steady growth of retail turnover indicators per capita (Table 1). At the same time, the annual growth rate of this indicator was observed to decrease during the studied period, as long as the average annual growth rate according to the forecast parameters of the state programs is not less than 120%.

Table 1.

Retail per capita in Samarkand region in 2017-2021

Trade turnover indicators □

No	The name of the indicator	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
1	Total retail turnover per capita, thousand soum, including:	1151.3	1400.9	1698.3	2102.2	2446.5
	In the city	2398.4	3114.1	3917.8	4903.8	5860.4
	In the village	928.9	1129.5	1376.6	1656.2	1741.3
	Consumer price index	1,068	1,061	1,056	1,057	1,114
2	Growth rate of retail turnover per capita, % compared to the previous year including	114.2	113.9	114.8	117.1	104.4
	In the city	120.5	122.4	119.1	118.4	107.2
	In the village	115.2	114.6	115.4	113.8	94.4
3	Per capita in urban and rural areas right coming retail ratio of sales turnover	2.6:1	2.75:1	2.84:1	2.96:1	3.36:1

According to the analyzed indicators, it was found that the rural population is far behind the urban population. For example, retail turnover per capita in rural areas is 3.3 times lower than in urban areas. In the course of the analysis, it was found that there is a big difference in the provision of trade services across the districts, which confirms the need for a separate approach to each district. Therefore, one of the most important tasks of improving the efficiency of the provision of trade services in rural areas is to eliminate the existing imbalance.

Solving this issue is related, on the one hand, to the development of economic relations in the system of trade services, and on the other hand, to the improvement of methodological aspects of the assessment of the effectiveness of trade services.

The first direction: depends on improving the activity of trade entrepreneurship entities. We have analyzed the distribution of retail turnover among the subjects of trade services. The results of the research indicate the increasing role of farmers' markets and trade complexes in the field of trade services in the region, which make up 63% of the total trade services volume. An in-depth analysis of various organizational forms of trade services provision made it possible to describe their strengths and weaknesses and became the basis for evaluating the prospects for the provision of trade services to the rural population.

As a result of the conducted research, we found it necessary to include the following in the generalized indicators of the provision of commercial services to the population:

- indicator of retail turnover per capita reflecting the level of development of retail trade in the region;
- indicator of gross consumer spending of the population, which reflects the socio-economic interests of consumers;

- an economic indicator of the activity of trade organizations that reflects the economic interests of subjects of trade services.

In turn, each generalized indicator consists of specific indicators of the provision of trade services, because their complexity does not allow to be expressed by a single formula.

As a result of the conducted theoretical and practical research, we came to the conclusion that the level of trade services in rural areas should be evaluated through a system of indicators of a different socio-economic nature.

Economically, the application of this approach can serve to objectively evaluate the state of the existing system of trade services in rural districts. Based on this, it will be possible to identify the socially necessary trade services, that is, to remove the subjective evaluations of the trade services from the gross income of trade organizations, and at the same time, to create a favorable trade environment and add the services of studying the demand of the population.

During the research period, it became clear that today, when evaluating the effectiveness of providing commercial services to the population, consumption aspects are not given enough attention. Clarification of the terms "consumer" and "buyer" is important from a scientific and methodological point of view in revealing the characteristics of the formation of the population's demand for goods. Ensuring consumer choice, that is, the availability of the possibility to satisfy demand in a more efficient way, forms the methodological basis of consumer aspects of evaluation. At different stages of demand formation, villagers perform different roles: among others, as a carrier of needs, then as a buyer, and at the final stage as a consumer. Economically, the application of this approach can serve to objectively evaluate the state of the existing system of trade services in rural districts.

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The study of different groups of rural residents made it possible to reveal certain regularities in their consumer behavior. Based on this, in our dissertation study, the consumer behavior process of rural residents was developed (Fig. 2). This process shows the socio-economic nature of decision-making about the place, time and nature of shopping. The application of this approach contributes to the development of scientific views on the formation of demand for consumer goods in rural areas and allows to understand the subjective evaluation of the efficiency of the trade service delivery system by buyers. Taking into account the social origin of consumer spending, a questionnaire survey method was used, because, on the one hand,

More than 300 citizens from three districts of Samarkand region were involved as respondents. The survey is structured in such a way that the answers to the questions cover all groups of consumer spending. In the analysis of the results of the survey, three types of attitudes were distinguished for each indicator of gross consumption expenditure of the population: positive, indifferent and negative. This made it possible to quantify the level of satisfaction of the need for trade services by consumers.

As a result of processing, the response of consumers can be explained with the following tabular data (Table 2).

Table 2

Consumer demand for goods and services
Their relationship to satisfaction costs □

No	The name of the indicator	Consumers relationship distribution of responses, %		
		Positive	Indifferent	Negative
1	Consumption of demand formation with associated costs	45.0	23.0	32.0
2	Costs associated with searching for goods	46.7	11.7	41.6
3	Sold before deal make up with depends expenses	32.5	45.0	22.5
4	From sale next service show with associated costs	56.7	13.3	30.0

Most of the consumers positively evaluated the state of providing trade services to the population. For example, 45% of those who participated in the survey positively evaluated the costs associated with the formation of consumer demand, 46.7% the costs associated with searching for goods, and 56.7% the costs associated with providing after-sales service, that is, the current state of sales services is in line with their expectations. . The presence of a negative relationship in consumer responses indicates that there are opportunities to improve the effectiveness of sales services in the regions.

Based on the results of the survey, it became possible to assess the level of satisfaction of the population, namely:

$$KQ = \frac{\sum (K_{qi})}{4}$$

Here: $K_{iq} = (N - N_{is}) / N$ – level of satisfaction according to the i-type of consumer spending;

N - total number of respondents;

N_{is} is negative on the i-index number of respondents who responded.

This indicator makes it possible to determine the attitude of the rural population to the state of retail trade and the content of trade services, and to assess the actual level of the provision of trade services to the population. Then it will be possible to evaluate the effectiveness of the provision of trade services in the village with the integrated indicator of the retail trade turnover, which includes the consumption costs of the population and the gross income of the subjects of trade services. At the same time, the advantage of this approach is manifested in decision-making taking into account the needs of the population in each district.

We recommend the practical application of this formula by periodic surveys of consumption expenditures in the course of household surveys by statistical authorities.

Figure 2. Strategic directions for increasing the efficiency of the provision of trade services to the rural population

It is dedicated to the development and scientific justification of strategic directions for increasing the efficiency of trade services in rural settlements (Fig. 2).

These directions include reconstruction of the system of providing trade services in rural areas, provision of trade services, intensification and updating of their content. Each sub-system is aimed at fulfilling specific tasks to improve the level of satisfaction of the population's needs and the efficiency of retail trade.

The main source of increasing the efficiency of trade services is to increase the number of trade entities and strengthen their material and technical base. According to the data, the level of provision of commercial areas in rural areas is much lower than in cities. Therefore, prospective plans for the placement of retail trade entities will be a priority for improving trade services for the population.

Factors affecting the provision of trade services to the rural population are studied, and the factors with general influence reflect the level of development of the trade and consumer market in the area and have the same effect on all residential areas.

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